

Enabling an Open Innovation Model for EU Toy Industry SMEs through Co-Creation with FabLabs, Safety Experts and Customer Communities

WP3- ToyLabs Added-Value Components Design and Development

Deliverable D3.4: "ToyLabs Added-Value Components Design and Development-v3"

TOYLABS

ENABLING AN OPEN INNOVATION MODEL FOR EU TOY INDUSTRY SMES
THROUGH CO-CREATION WITH FABLABS, SAFETY EXPERTS AND CUSTOMER
COMMUNITIES

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**ToyLabs Added-Value Components Design and
Development-v3**

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ABBREVIATIONS LIST

ARF	Augmented Reality Feedback
ARFC	Augmented Reality Feedback Component
MTA	Market Trend Analysis
MVP	Minimum Viable Product
PMN	Partner Matching and Negotiation
TCP	ToyLabs Core Platform

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Deliverable D3.4 titled as “ToyLabs Added-Value Components Design and Development-v3” is used to document the updated designs regarding the components the design and development of which has been completed after the delivery of D3.3. Specifically, following the ToyLabs Core Platform and the Market Analysis Component already documented, the present deliverable describes the Partner Matching & Negotiation component and the Augmented Reality Feedback component and updates the design and flows which have been presented in D3.2.

The deliverable has the nature of a “Demonstrator”, therefore the document at hand acts as an accompanying text to the designs, workflow diagrams and other work that has been performed under the WP3 tasks in the previous period. All these outputs, can be found in the project’s GitHub repository, located at <https://github.com/singularlogic/ToyLabs>

D3.4 will be updated throughout the project and those amendments will result to deliverable D3.5. It provides new insights and design documentation to the tasks of WP4, describing the features and functions of the components which are integrated leading to a complete version of the ToyLabs Platform.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Purpose and scope

Deliverable D3.4 titled as “ToyLabs Added-Value Components Design and Development-v3” is used to document the updated versions and designs of the ToyLabs components that have been introduced since the previous software components development cycle in the framework of WP3.

In D3.3 the two components that had been prioritised, the **ToyLabs Core Platform** and the **Market Analysis Component** were described in detail as far as it concerns their architecture and operation.

In the present document, the other two components which have been developed in order to get integrated in the ToyLabs Platform, the **Partner Matching & Negotiation Component** and the **Augmented Reality Feedback Component** are described in a similar way.

The deliverable has the nature of a “Demonstrator”, therefore the document at hand acts as an accompanying text to the designs, workflow diagrams and other work that has been performed under the WP3 tasks in the previous period. All these outputs, can be found in the project’s GitHub repository, located at <https://github.com/singularlogic/ToyLabs>

1.2 Structure of the deliverable

D3.4 is structured as follows:

- Section 2 presents the updates to the work started and presented in D3.2 towards defining the high level architecture, the flows and the actual operation of the Partner Matching & Negotiation component
- Section 3 refers to the Augmented Reality Feedback component, which actually consists of a server side sub-component which shall get integrated in the ToyLabs platform and a mobile sub-component which is compiled as a mobile app that can be downloaded by anyone who has compatible device.
- Section 4 concludes the deliverable, stating the next imminent steps to be executed and documented under the deliverable D3.5

1.3 Relation to other ToyLabs WPs and Tasks

As identified in the DoA, D3.4 is tightly linked to all other WP3 deliverables, as well as to all WP4 Deliverables.

Regarding WP3, D3.4, could be considered as the second revision of D3.2 and continuation of D3.3 (which consists the first revision of D3.2). The aforementioned reports will be further revised throughout the project and will serve as the basis for

deliverable D3.5, which concerns the final designs and technical diagrams of all the added value components developed in the framework of the project.

With regards to WP4, D3.4 provides updates to specific design documents, which are taken into account during the development tasks. Furthermore, D3.4, like all WP3 deliverables, is expected to act as reference document regarding the evaluation of the output of the software development tasks.

2 PARTNER MATCHING & NEGOTIATION COMPONENT (UPDATE)

2.1 Introduction

The Partner Matching & Negotiation (PMN) component is a tool that can be used by users to inquire about collaborators, inside the Toylabs Platform, allowing them to set up formal partnerships, that will lead to collaborative design and development of products.

In more detail, the PMN component is responsible for handling a handful of operations that range from partner searching to matchmaking between different platform users, enabling specific collaboration opportunities.

2.2 Updated Component's High-Level Architecture

The PMN component is an infrastructure that relies on a three-tier architecture.

The backend consists of a MySQL database which is being used to store data regarding the different partners, as well as other information, such as active or past collaborations. The middle layer is responsible for the application logic and executes the partner search queries as well as the different partner matching algorithms.

A high-level description of the TCP architecture is provided in the following figure.

Figure 1: PMN High Level Architecture

More specifically, the updated PMN High Level Architecture consists of:

The **User Interface**, which in turn consists of:

- The **Searching Interface**, which gives us the opportunity to search for a partner, by name or by matching criteria
- The **Negotiations/Messaging Interface**, which makes the exchange of messages, between the interested parties, feasible, in order to, start a collaboration, exchange contracts, or other legal documents
- The **Evaluation Interface**, setting the platform for the partners to evaluate and provide feedback on their collaboration, when a project is closed or archived.

The **PMN component logic**, composed of:

- The **Partner Matching Query Engine**, which is responsible for collecting data from the Search Interface and to provide ratings for the Partner Info, Capabilities and Feedback Repository.
- The **Partner Engagement Engine**, in order for a collaboration to initiate, but also for monitoring the collaboration status
- The **Partner Evaluation Engine**, liable to collect feedback on every partner, aggregating the provided feedback on their collaborations, so that their ratings can be summed up.

The **Toylabs Platform Database**, formed by:

- The **Partner Info, Capabilities and Feedback Repository**, in order to collect data on each partner, in any collaboration, providing data to this effect
- The **Collaboration Status Repository**, which stores the collaboration status (pending, active, negotiating, etc.)
 - The **Negotiations Repository**, where the discussions on a collaboration agreement are stored, as well as, contract and non-disclosure agreement documents.

2.3 Updated Component's Flow Diagram

The PMN component's main objective is to allow users to seek for collaborators. This is based on the process of triggering a query which returns the possible collaborators that match the user's search criteria, which can be constantly refined until a short list is displayed. Out of the short list, the user may choose a preferred potential collaborator and send an NDA accompanied by a collaboration request. A negotiation among the two parties takes place with the support of the component,

including exchange of documents and draft agreements. A successful negotiation leads to exchanging and storing the contract which defines the agreement terms and can be used by involved parties as reference document.

The following diagram represents the workflow defining the operation of the component:

Figure 2: PMN Flow Architecture

2.4 Step by step component's operation

As the development of the platform has progressed, a walkthrough of the component can be presented in order to demonstrate its operation. Indicative screenshots are provided presenting the different screens of the Partner Matching and Negotiations Component and documented in the present section.

1. Searching for collaborators

Any product owner has access to the PMN component through which he may seek for potential collaborators either on new or on existing designs, as shown in the following screenshot.

The screenshot displays the Toylabs Platform interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the Toylabs logo, menu items for Dashboard, Members, and About, and user information for Marios Phinikettos. Below the navigation bar, the main content area is titled "Product Designs" and includes a "Back to Dashboard" button. A table lists four product designs, each with a title, version number, last modified date, and a set of action icons. A "Collaborations" tooltip is visible over the action icons of the first design. At the bottom right of the table, there is a blue button labeled "+ Add Design".

Title	Version	Last Modified	Actions
Design A	1	04.10.2017	[Edit] [View] [Refresh] [Share] [Collaborations] [More]
Aspernatur velit dolore	1	04.10.2017	[Edit] [View] [Refresh] [Share] [Collaborations] [More]
Id recusandae molestiae.	1	06.07.2017	[Edit] [View] [Refresh] [Share] [Collaborations] [More]
Voluptatem enim laborum.	1	06.07.2017	[Edit] [View] [Refresh] [Share] [Collaborations] [More]

2. Searching potential collaborators

A user of Toylabs Platform can search for a partner to collaborate either directly by providing the name of a specific company/ organisation participating in the platform or by defining certain criteria. The two options are being demonstrated in the figures below.

Collaborations

Design: Design A

[← Back to Designs](#)

Overview Search

Q

ADVANCED SEARCH

I am looking for a: Toy Manufacturer FabLab Child Expert Safety Expert

That has any the following competencies:

<input type="checkbox"/> 3D Modelling	<input type="checkbox"/> 3D Printing	<input type="checkbox"/> 3D Scanning
<input type="checkbox"/> CAE/FEM and Structural Analysis Simulation	<input type="checkbox"/> Circuit Production	<input type="checkbox"/> CNC Milling
<input type="checkbox"/> Inkjet Printing	<input type="checkbox"/> Knitting Machine	<input type="checkbox"/> Laser Cutting
<input type="checkbox"/> Mould Casting	<input type="checkbox"/> Plastic Transformation	<input type="checkbox"/> Sewing Machine
<input type="checkbox"/> Soldering Station	<input type="checkbox"/> Vacuum Forming	<input type="checkbox"/> Vinyl Cutting

Scale of production needed: Prototyping Only Small Medium Large Extra Large

I will pay using: Bank Transfer Credit Card Paypal Check Bitcoin

Payment will be: On Delivery In 15 Days In 30 Days In 45 Days In 60 Days In 90 Days

Clear
Search

Search by certain criteria screen

Collaborations

Design: Design A

[← Back to Designs](#)

Overview Search

Q

Singular Logic

✔ Toy Manufacturer

That has any the following competencies:

<input type="checkbox"/> 3D Modelling	<input type="checkbox"/> 3D Printing	<input type="checkbox"/> 3D Scanning
<input type="checkbox"/> CAE/FEM and Structural Analysis Simulation	<input type="checkbox"/> Circuit Production	<input type="checkbox"/> CNC Milling
<input type="checkbox"/> Inkjet Printing	<input type="checkbox"/> Knitting Machine	<input type="checkbox"/> Laser Cutting
<input type="checkbox"/> Mould Casting	<input type="checkbox"/> Plastic Transformation	<input type="checkbox"/> Sewing Machine
<input type="checkbox"/> Soldering Station	<input type="checkbox"/> Vacuum Forming	<input type="checkbox"/> Vinyl Cutting

Scale of production needed: Prototyping Only Small Medium Large Extra Large

I will pay using: Bank Transfer Credit Card Paypal Check Bitcoin

Payment will be: On Delivery In 15 Days In 30 Days In 45 Days In 60 Days In 90 Days

Clear
Search

Search by name screen

3. Criteria Matching

On the basis of the criteria defined, a list of organisations/ experts which cover them is being presented. The user has the opportunity to review all available information coming from the profile of each potential collaborator and after choosing the one which covers all parameters a negotiation session begins.

Negotiation takes place through a direct secure messaging system allowing the exchange of specific documents, like an NDA Agreement which is considered as very important to be signed from both parties, technical documents in order to define exact needs, financial offers and at the end exchange of contacts setting up the collaboration.

The user can start the negotiation session for a new collaboration by pressing the “Contact” button. After a successful negotiation, as well as in specific cases that no negotiation is needed (like when a collaboration contract already exists among the two partners), an agreed collaboration is being introduced for a specific design or prototype by pressing the “Add” button, as seen in the next screenshot.

Collaborations Design: Design A [Back to Designs](#)

Overview **Search**

Search by name...

ADVANCED SEARCH

I am looking for a: Toy Manufacturer FabLab Child Expert Safety Expert

That has any the following competencies:

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 3D Modelling	<input type="checkbox"/> 3D Printing	<input type="checkbox"/> 3D Scanning
<input type="checkbox"/> CAE/FEM and Structural Analysis Simulation	<input type="checkbox"/> Circuit Production	<input type="checkbox"/> CNC Milling
<input type="checkbox"/> Inkjet Printing	<input type="checkbox"/> Knitting Machine	<input type="checkbox"/> Laser Cutting
<input type="checkbox"/> Mould Casting	<input type="checkbox"/> Plastic Transformation	<input type="checkbox"/> Sewing Machine
<input type="checkbox"/> Soldering Station	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Vacuum Forming	<input type="checkbox"/> Vinyl Cutting

Scale of production needed: Prototyping Only Small Medium Large Extra Large

I will pay using: Bank Transfer Credit Card Paypal Check Bitcoin

Payment will be: On Delivery In 15 Days In 30 Days In 45 Days In 60 Days In 90 Days

[Clear](#) [Search](#)

Search results

1. Singular Logic ISO9001

Toy Manufacturer:

SingularLogic is the No 1 Greek Software Vendor and one of the largest Integrated IT Solutions Group in Greece. Its activities comprise of the development and distribution of business software applications, design and implementation of Integrated IT Solutions for large enterprises of the private and public sector, including distribution and support of well-established international IT products. SingularLogic, member of Marfin Investment Group, has highly skilled personnel, specialized know ...

3D Modelling Vacuum Forming [Contact](#) [Add](#)

Initiating a collaboration

4. The terms of the collaboration

Before adding someone to a collaboration, certain terms are being discussed and negotiated. An exchange of documents (NDA agreement, contracts, etc.) can be used, so that the interested parties reach an agreement.

TOYLABS Dashboard Members About

Collaborations Design: Design A

Overview Search **Singular Logic**

Important
Before you add someone to your design, make sure you discuss and agree on the terms of your collaboration. If needed, you can use the form below to attach and exchange documents (e.g. NDA agreements, contracts, etc) to help you reach an agreement.

Drop files here to upload

Add as collaborator Send

Negotiation of the terms and Exchange of contracts

5. Joining a collaboration

The next screenshot shows a user added as a collaborator to an existing design/ prototype model.

TOYLABS Dashboard Members About

My Products **Collaborations** Archive

+ New Product Search...

Name	Product	Version	Last Modified
Lorem	Toy B	1	4 days ago

As long as a new partner is being introduced as collaborator in a specific design or prototype, all privately-shared data regarding the toy under development become

available to him. The actual collaboration (in terms of technical work) does not of course take place in the platform, however all files, designs and technical documents are exchanged and monitored through the platform. In order to help in more fruitful collaborations avoiding conflicts, all activities are being timestamped in the platform, making it easy to identify which is the case when any disagreement appears between two collaborators.

3 AUGMENTED REALITY FEEDBACK COMPONENT (UPDATE)

3.1 Introduction

The Augmented Reality Feedback Component (ARF Component or ARFC) is a tool used by end user that allow responsive and interactive presentation of 3D models with advanced capabilities.

Main goal of this tool is to obtain feedback and related recommendations for improving new product designs.

The ARFC will use 3 different modules: Questionnaire Creation to obtain feedback from user, Augmented Reality System for model presentation (rotation, modifying parameters like color, textures, etc) and Voting System used to know specific features on an AR model on mobile devices.

3.2 Component's High-level Architecture

The ARF component is an infrastructure that relies also on a three-tier architecture.

The backend consists of an MySQL¹ database with several tables which is being used to store server path for previously uploaded 3D models, textures or other parameters on one side on other side a table should be defined with standard tracking parameters ready to be used by end user or product owner (jpg, pdf, ...)

On the User side the ARF component is supported by a survey infrastructure that can help products owners and end users to obtain feedback and related recommendations for improving new product designs. This survey infrastructure will be integrated on general survey engine module.

Also on user side, the ARF component will use a Voting System, this infrastructure will be integrated using general voting engine module developed on platform.

¹ <https://www.mysql.com>

Figure 3: ARF High Level Architecture

The Toylabs iOS Application is built on latest iOS SDK (11.2) using Swift version 4. The minimum iOS version supported is iOS 11.0. In order to retrieve and send the required data, the app sends HTTP Requests to a RESTful API. The supported formats for ar-models are the following: *.fbx*, *.obj*, *.3ds*, *.stl*, *.dae*, *.scn*.

For the presentation of AR-models, the app uses apple's AR Kit.

3.3 Component's Flow Diagrams

As indicated in D2.1, the ARF component is used to allow users (Childhood Experts/End-Users, Childhood Experts/End-Users, FabLabs ,...) to send feedback to the owners/ developers of a product on predefined 3D Models and product definition.

The figure below presents the workflow performed by a product that is willing to showcase an AR model. He is able to check for existing material on the platform, develop new material and after defining the target audience launch the AR model and explore the results of the feedback.

Figure 4: ARF Manufacturer Workflow

On the other side, the following figure shows how experts, FabLabs and other individuals or organizations are able to select an AR model (probably on their mobile phone), explore it through its visualization features and then provide feedback to the manufacturer, that could be either in the form of a structured questionnaire, or through a voting system.

Figure 5: ARF End users Workflow

3.4 Step by step component's operation

3.4.1 Product Owner perspective

1. The product owner can attach to each Design (or Prototype - the Augmented Reality module is available for both Designs and Prototypes in the exact same way), one or more AR models for getting feedback on that asset (Design or Prototype). We tried to make the process as easy and quick as possible, because we believe that AR is an invaluable part while designing a new toy,

and a way to differentiate the ToyLabs platform from any generic collaboration platforms available.

2. Any user of the product owning organization, can access the AR models page for a Design using the 'eye' icon in the design actions. On that page, the user can see all models attached to that design and can edit or delete them (any feedback provided by end-users or collaborators is lost when a model is deleted).

3. For each model, an overview that includes Number of Downloads, Average Rating and Number of Comments received so far is provided.
4. Clicking on a model, a full analysis of what users believe, is presented to the user (img. 3). On this page, the product owner can see average rating for each question asked, a breakdown of the ratings per question and rating given and the comments provided by the users.

Hurray! My second AR model!

Feedback for design: Lorem

[← Back to AR Models](#)

Some text can go here as well!

Average Ratings

4.33 MY DESIGN

3.67 SUPER FEATURES

3.67 NOVELTY

Analysis of Responses

Question	★ ★ ★ ★ ★	★ ★ ★ ★ ☆	★ ★ ★ ★ ☆	★ ★ ★ ★ ☆	★ ★ ★ ★ ☆
My Design	0	0	1	0	2
Super Features	0	1	0	1	1
Novelty	1	0	0	0	2

Comments (2)

Marios Phinikettos 1 week ago

Test comments!

[Reply](#) [Delete](#)

Marios Phinikettos 1 week ago

Testing API feedback!

[Reply](#) [Delete](#)

- As we said before, creating an AR model for a design is as straight forward as choosing the “Create AR model” in the AR models page, filling a quick form and uploading the model files (img. 4).

Create AR Model

[← Back to AR Models](#)

Title

Description

Use this field to explain to users:

- what to expect,
- how to use the model,
- possible shortcomings,
- what to test,
- whatever you think is necessary to know before they use the model.

Files

For the model to work correctly, all the nodes of the 3D model should be under a parent node and that parent node should have the exact same name as the filename of the model. Keep in mind that, when opened in the ToyLabs app, the front of the model will be displayed, so make sure it is designed accordingly. **Supported file types:** fbx, obj, 3ds, stl, dae, stl (and image files for use as textures).

Drop files here to upload

Questions

Users that download your AR model will be asked to rate it based on a number of criteria (change to suit your specific needs). Rating will be done using a scale of 1-5.

Question 1	Design
Question 2	Features
Question 3	Novelty

6. For each model, the user is asked to provide a short title of the model (this is how the model will be listed in the ToyLabs app), enter a description for the user and enter 3 questions that can be answered using a 5-star rating system. The description can be an explanation to the users about what this toy is about, how to use the model, what kind of feedback is expected from them etc. Remember, the AR models are not to be used for finished products (even though that's possible), but for getting feedback from collaborators (usually child and security experts) early on the toy creation process.

Augmented Reality Models

Design: Lorem

[← Back to Designs](#)

Title	Downloads	Comments	Rating	Actions
Hurray! My second AR model!	1	2	3.89	
gbikas ar	2	1	3.33	
Cherub test	1	4	3.25	
cherub dae	0	0	0.00	
new dae file	0	0	0.00	
neww dae	2	1	3.67	

[+ Add AR Model](#)

3.4.2 End User (Provider of feedback) perspective

1. The User opens the Toylabs mobile app. The login screen is presented. User has three options to authenticate (email, facebook, google).

2. After successful login, user is redirected to the main view of the app, where he can see a list of AR models (title, average rating, thumbnail). These include models that belong to (a) public products, (b) public designs or prototypes, (c) their own (or their organisations') products and (d) designs or prototypes they are collaborating on.

By tapping the top left button, user can sort the list by title, average rating or date.

3. After an ar-model of the list is selected, the user is presented with the details of that ar-model. User can download the ar-model file (or delete it).

4. By tapping the “Open AR Camera” button, the camera of the phone is activated. User has to wait 2-3 seconds in order to allow the AR camera to orient itself.

The user can tap anywhere in the screen and the AR model will be placed in that place. The model is anchored to the specific point the user tapped, so the user can go around the model and observe it. If he taps on the already placed model, then it disappears. When user finishes observing the AR model, he taps the “Rate Model” button and he is presented with the questionnaire.

5. User must rate 3 questions by selecting an amount of stars (1-5) for each question. Afterwards the user has the option to leave a comment and then tap submit.

Any Comments? (Optional)

Design

6. In order to logout, user must go back to the main view and tap his profile pic in the top right corner. User is presented with his profile view, in which he has the option to logout.

vf GR 4G 10:57 72%

gbikas

About

Acknowledgements

Logout

4 CONCLUSIONS

4.1 At a glance

D3.4 includes the updated design documents which are provided for the development of Partner Matching and Negotiation component, as well as for the Augmented Reality Feedback component, which are the components on which most effort has been put during the reference period from the delivery of D3.3 to date.

All progress and the latest updated data which formulate the core material upon which WP4 works to deliver the software platform, are available the project's GitHub account at <https://github.com/singularlogic/ToyLabs>.

As an update to D3.2, the present deliverable introduces some changes and additions to be considered during the development of the ToyLabs platform.

4.2 Next Steps

As discussed in the introduction, D3.4 will be updated based on the feedback expected from the trial users and by incorporating all changes it will lead to D3.5. Such changes will also propagate to the software development tasks of WP4, in order to complete the features and functions necessary to reach the final version of the ToyLabs platform.